

The Art of Diagnosis in the Works of Askar Mahkam

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Abstract: *Sufi poet Askar Mahkam has continued the mystical tradition of classical poetry with distinction. This article analyzes the examples of the art of diagnosis in Askar Mahkam's works, one of the poetic devices that defines the aesthetics of our classical poetry.*

Keywords: *Diagnosis, artistic depiction, mysticism, poetry, human, object, expressiveness.*

Introduction

The art of diagnosis, or “animation,” is the technique of attributing human qualities to animals, birds, and inanimate objects. Through this approach, poets more clearly express particular ideas, while the depicted lyrical or epic images gain brightness, liveliness, and allure. This poetic device indirectly presents ideas, “wrapped in paper,” so to speak. In Uzbek literature, Gulkhani’s “Zarbulmasal” and the Indian work “Kalila and Dimna” are based on this art form, using the actions and behaviors of animals to reveal human flaws and negative traits. In some works and lyrical pieces, the art of diagnosis also enhances expressiveness by breathing life into inanimate objects.

The poet Askar Mahkam, known for his mastery in creating unique expressions, offers beautiful examples of the art of diagnosis in his poetry. For instance, the following lines serve as proof of our point:

“Autumn... the last leaves fall,
Wrinkling the lips of the trees.
Bare willows dream,
Like ancient narrators.”

In this excerpt from the poem “Landscape,” the poet describes the leaves as “falling” instead of “shedding,” emphasizing a harder and more deliberate descent. The leaves fall as if they were people, while the bare trees in the third and fourth lines acquire the human trait of contemplating, like ancient storytellers.

Literature review and methods

Literary devices lend each word and expression a unique spirit and beauty, which is why we refer to them as “artistic.” Through the art of diagnosis, inanimate objects “move” like humans, illuminating our artistic imagination and providing aesthetic pleasure. An example of the art of diagnosis in Mahkam’s poem “Left behind...” includes the lines:

“The autumn gardens wipe their tears,
Your dark hair’s breezes brush them away.
The struggle for life,
The trees tell with leaves shedding.”

When analyzed for meaning, these lines carry profound connotations. Superficially, they seem simple, but they contain a mystical layer. Alisher Navoi equates old age to autumn; Mahkam, too, depicts the hardships of old age in “autumn gardens.” Here, “dark hair” represents worldly desires, and “breezes”

stand for unfulfilled dreams, suggesting that no matter one's stage in life, they are not free from yearning for the pleasures of life. This theme is also present in Navoi's couplet:

“Though one ages,

Two traits of youth remain:

Greed and the long hopes he entertains.”

In Navoi's couplet, the hardships of aging are described alongside two qualities that persist: desire and ambition. Mahkam conveys a similar sentiment in his lines: life is a struggle, where one faces numerous hardships and conflicts. No matter the situation, life is a fight to survive. The world's harshness continues to shake the tree of our lives, shedding its leaves one by one. The poet's portrayal of “hair brushing away tears” and trees “telling tales of life's struggle” beautifully exemplifies the art of diagnosis.

Discussion and results

“Existence spreads pure scents,

The moon fills a royal goblet with milk.

On the shores, swans shed tears,

While the river carries its funeral waves.

Clouds shake off stardust smoke,

And bears that devour the mountains descend.”

In this excerpt from Mahkam's poem Tavajjuh, which reflects the thoughts and life of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, we find instances of the art of diagnosis. “Swans shedding tears” exemplifies this art, as crying is a human trait. Similarly, the portrayal of clouds shaking stardust and “the world dipping its snout into the royal goblet” are other beautiful examples of the art of diagnosis. The poet compares the moon to a royal goblet filled with milk, but the world's interference has tainted this pure goblet, symbolizing how the world's deception has left stains on the moon's face.

Conclusion

“The soul hangs the body on a high scaffold,

If it doesn't kill each moment, it's already dead.”

These lines from the poet's mystical piece Love reflect the tension between body and soul in Sufi thought, where the body represents worldly attachments, while the soul represents eternal existence. In sufism, the body is seen as transient, while the soul is eternal. To reach perfection, the soul must renounce the body's worldly temptations and ego. If it succumbs to temporary desires and pride, it has, in effect, ceased to live meaningfully. The imagery of the soul “killing” the body is a remarkable example of the art of diagnosis.

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